

Individualised Learning at Geneva Christian College: Analysis with PAT Maths Data

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Abstract

At Geneva Christian College, we have partnered with Maths Pathway since 2017, in order to target each student at their point of need. Since then, teachers report improvement in student engagement and problem-solving, as well as increases in NAPLAN Numeracy and PAT Maths scores. In this analysis, we build on the work of Steinbergs & Smith (2024) which examined PAT Maths and Maths Pathway data in a Victorian school, finding positive associations between Maths Pathway usage and PAT Maths attainment and growth. We find that Geneva Christian College data shows similar patterns, with students attaining approximately 1.51 years' growth per year as measured by PAT Maths. Maths Pathway has a minimum recommended dosage of 52 modules completed per year; we find that students who meet this threshold clearly outperform their peers on PAT Maths. These findings may be important for other schools aiming to lift outcomes, using a clear dosage target backed up by data.

Keywords: eLearning, mathematics, personalisation, mastery learning, differentiation, dosage, modules

Background

The School Context

Geneva Christian College caters to students from Kindergarten through to Year 12. Kindergarten uses the Early Years Learning Framework, the Australian Curriculum which is the basis for Prep to Year 10 students, with TASC being facilitated in the senior school. Year 12 students have the opportunity to complete either the Tasmanian Certificate of Education (TCE), a Vocational & Education Training (VET) course, or a school-based traineeship.

Geneva Christian College has a unique setting, positioned on the outskirts of Latrobe in north-west Tasmania on 123 acres. With approximately 300 students, Geneva Christian College has grown in recent years.

We desire to develop Christ-centred, Bible-based, worldview shaped approaches to Christian education. We employ the Transformation by Design – The Big Picture curriculum framework, a resource underpinning the school’s core values and that ensures a worldview shaped by the Bible as the foremost driver of how the curriculum is presented to students.

The goal for learning at the College is to support every student from their current point in their learning. This entails all students being on an individualised program that supports learning needs across years Prep to Year 10. We endeavour to work alongside parents and families to ensure students are on the right path socially, emotionally, spiritually and academically.

Differentiation with Maths Pathway

At Geneva Christian College, we knew of the findings of Australian research which indicated that “in any given year level, there is a five- to six-year difference between the most advanced and the least advanced ten percent of students”, with certain studies indicating that this gap can extend to as much as eight years in mathematics (Goss & Hunter, 2015). This phenomenon was evident within our own context: we observed that for a Year 7 cohort at the start of the school year, the gaps between student’s capabilities in Mathematics appeared to be at least eight years. Some students were lacking foundational understandings from Year 2, while others were capable of engaging with material at a Year 9 or 10 level.

In response to this disparity, Geneva Christian College initiated a partnership with Maths Pathway in 2017 to facilitate differentiated instruction that addresses students' individual needs,

promotes mastery, and enables all learners to progress along a continuum from their current level of understanding. This initiative is implemented across Years 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10.

Maths Pathway is “a sustainable, evidence-based programmatic approach to maximised teacher efficacy in delivering differentiated maths learning for students across Australia ... Critical to Maths Pathway’s success is the pedagogical model that empowers teachers to use assessments and evidence based pedagogical strategies effectively and efficiently.” (Sundar & Schenke, 2021).

While the implementation of Maths Pathway incorporates some technological elements, it is not merely an adjunct to traditional instruction. Our teaching teams continue to base the core of their instruction, their course planning, their assessment and their reporting in this model. They have established something cohesive and end-to-end that consistently targets each student's specific needs.

The Basis for this Analysis

School-level Data Observed so Far

Since implementing Maths Pathway in 2017 with our secondary students, we noticed students becoming more engaged learners, able to problem-solve worded equations more effectively and have seen improved growth in NAPLAN Numeracy and PAT Maths results in Year 9. This led us to the addition of Maths Pathway to Year 5 & 6 classes more recently, which we believe will result in an improvement in numeracy levels across all year levels. NAPLAN Numeracy data from 2024 suggests that both Year 7 & 9 have shown strong growth.

We are interested in further investigating the efficacy of our teaching approach through the utilisation of multiple data sources, specifically: PAT Maths growth, PAT Maths attainment, and Maths Pathway module dosage.

PAT Maths Data Collection

The Progressive Achievement Test for Mathematics (PAT Maths) is provided by the Australian Council for Education Research (ACER). PAT Maths aims to measure “...what students in Foundation to Year 10 know, understand and are capable of across domains, and help monitor progress over time.” (ACER, n.d.). Our students take this test annually early in Term Four of the school year (mid-late October), delivered through ACER’s online testing platform.

Maths Pathway Dosage Data Collection

Through Maths Pathway’s online platform, students’ 'dosage' is recorded year to year. This is a count of the number of ‘modules’ a student completed during each academic year, with each module typically taking around 30 minutes to complete. This dosage data indicates the extent to which the program was used by an individual student. Maths Pathway provides our school with a guideline recommendation of at least 52 modules completed per year as being an effective dosage level.

Module ‘mastery’ - the number of modules a student demonstrates they understand under test conditions - was also considered as a measure, as this metric could better capture the extent to which a student “used their time well” with the program. However, module completion ‘dosage’ was ultimately chosen as the appropriate proxy as it is a factor teachers are more able to influence with their students. A correlation between ‘dosage’ and PAT Maths growth or PAT

Maths attainment is much more actionable for schools and teachers. For example, it could factor into the expectations that teachers set and reinforce, day-to-day in the classroom.

Comparable analysis

We note that this analysis builds upon the work of Steinbergs & Smith (2024) in a Victorian school. In that analysis, “[...] students appeared to grow at 142% of the Australian norm, as measured by PAT Maths (approximately 1.4 years’ learning per year). [...] Moreover, the level of use of Maths Pathway appears to be directly associated with that strong performance.”

Key Research Questions

Drawing upon PAT Maths test data and Maths Pathway dosage data, in this analysis, we aim to explore:

- (a) how our students’ growth over time compares to Australian norms, as measured by PAT Maths data; and
- (b) how PAT Maths data differs between students who have met or exceeded the minimum recommended dosage level (52 modules per year) compared with their peers who have not met that threshold.

Data Sets

Students with PAT Maths Growth Results

PAT Maths results from 2021, 2022, and 2023 were considered. We looked specifically at results from Year 7 in 2021 and 2022; and then correspondingly from Year 8 in 2022 and 2023.

Due to some changes in enrolments and some absences on the day of the test, not all data points from Year 7 assessments matched with Year 8 assessments. Only data that matched across both time points was considered so growth across that period could be examined. This captured the large majority of students in these cohorts; the only students excluded were those without PAT Maths data available due to absence and/or students who were not enrolled at Geneva Christian College for the relevant time period.

Students with Year 8 PAT Maths data and relevant Maths Pathway dosage data

Maths Pathway dosage data from 2022 and 2023 was considered. Students who were not enrolled at Geneva Christian College during either of those years would not have any dosage data available. In this analysis, we were interested in Year 8 PAT Maths performance (a test common to all students in the data set), so looked at the dosage leading up to that test. That is, during the year a student sat their October Year 8 assessment.

With no unique identifiers common to both data sources, PAT Maths data and Maths Pathway dosage data were matched using students' names. In this data set, there was only one pair of students with the same first and last names, so they were excluded from the analysis to remove any risk of ambiguity. The matched data was used for all analyses. The resulting data set pertained to 47 students, of which 25 were in Year 7 in 2021 and 22 were in Year 7 in 2022. This captured the large majority of students in these cohorts.

Analysis and Results

Student Growth from Year to Year

The results of each PAT Maths test include a 'PAT scale score' for each student. This is effectively a Rasch scale used across each year's assessment. "Scale scores are measured on an interval scale. This means that a difference of 5 in scale scores in the middle of the PAT scale (for example, from 50 to 55) is equivalent to the same difference on any other part of the scale (for example, from 15 to 20 or from 85 to 90)." This allows students' growth to be measured over time (ACER, 2011).

Australian norms show that the Year 7 students are expected to average a PAT scale score of 131.6; and Year 8 students 133.6 (ACER, 2022). This means the typical growth expected between Year 7 and Year 8 is approximately 2.0 points on the PAT scale. This gives a benchmark that can be used to see whether students are making at least 1 year's growth per year - by growing by at least 2.0 points on the PAT Maths scale from their Year 7 assessment to their Year 8 assessment.

Examining students' average attainment on Year 7 and 8 PAT Maths, the average growth shown in our data set is 3.02 points on the PAT scale. This is substantially higher than the 2.0 benchmark (approximately 51% higher), as pictured in Figure 1. If we take 2.0 points to represent 1 year's growth, then we would estimate that our students were making 1.51 years' growth each year.

Figure 1

Average increase over 1 year (7 to 8)

Figure 1: Typical annual growth between Year 7 and Year 8 as measured by PAT Maths against Australian norms (ACER, 2022), compared with the measured average PAT Maths growth between Year 7 and Year 8 at Geneva Christian College N = 47 students. This indicates that Geneva Christian College students are growing in mathematical attainment by approximately 1.51 years per academic year.

These results appear very strong. It seems likely that using Maths Pathway contributed to achieving this success - since it is embedded so deeply into teachers' practice day to day.

Student PAT Maths Performance and Maths Pathway Dosage

We consider student performance in Year 8 PAT Maths. This test is common to all 47 students in the data set, with 25 sitting the test in 2022 and 22 in 2023. For each student, we consider their PAT scale score. We compare this against their Maths Pathway dosage in the lead-up to that test - that is, the total number of modules completed in Year 8 for those students.

Maths Pathway has a guideline for a minimum effective dosage of 52 modules per year. This is equivalent to an average of 4 modules completed per Topic Test across 13 Units in the year. We find that of the 47 students in the data set, 35 (74%) met this requirement. Comparing this “high dosage” group against the other students shows a very noticeable difference in Year 8 PAT Maths attainment. Figure 2 shows that the median student in the high dosage group was higher than typical Year 8 attainment. The median in the lower dosage group was substantially lower than typical Year 7 attainment.

Figure 2

Figure 2: PAT scaled score on Year 8 PAT Maths in 2022 and 2023 at Geneva Christian College N = 47 students. Students are separated into two groups, based on whether they met Maths Pathway’s recommended minimum dosage (at least 52 modules completed per year) in the year of their Year 8 PAT assessment. Australian norm data for Year 7 and Year 8 PAT scaled score averages are shown for reference by dotted lines (ACER, 2022).

We note that the majority of students in our data set met or exceeded the baseline threshold for “high dosage”. The same was true in Steinberg and Smith’s (2024) analysis of a Victorian school. This may indicate that such a baseline expectation is practical and attainable across multiple school contexts.

Conclusion

In the context of Geneva Christian College’s implementation of Maths Pathway, we set out to explore (a) whether our students were growing rapidly in maths attainment from year to year; and (b) whether students who met or exceeded the minimum recommended dosage level of 52 modules per year had stronger outcomes than their peers.

Data for 47 middle school students from 2021 to 2023 showed that our students appeared to grow at 151% of the Australian norm, as measured by PAT Maths (approximately 1.51 years’ learning per year). Students with a higher level of use of the learning tool - whose dosage exceeded 52 modules per year - performed better on Year 8 PAT Maths than those with a lower dosage. 74% of students met or exceeded this dosage threshold; and had median attainment lying above that which is typical for Year 8 PAT Maths.

These results are consistent with strong PAT Maths attainment and growth for students using Maths Pathway, particularly when their usage meets or exceeds the recommended threshold of 52 modules per unit. This was consistent with the findings of Steinbergs & Smith (2024) within a Victorian school.

This finding may have implications within our school and in other schools as well. It may be that teaching teams target, say, 95% of students meeting or exceeding that threshold. If there are 13 Units through the year, a target of 4 modules completed per Unit would result in the

desired 52 modules per year. However, it could be worth considering a higher expectation being conveyed to students to provide a margin of safety - say, at least 5 modules completed each Unit - to ensure that only a small proportion fall below the actual recommended dosage level.

Overall, the results of this analysis indicate rapid student learning at Geneva Christian College while implementing Maths Pathway. Drawing upon PAT Maths data allows our teaching team to consider what goals and expectations to set for students, while also giving confidence that the formative observations of our teaching staff appear to be correct - that, working with Maths Pathway, we are having a substantial and meaningful impact on student learning and outcomes.

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